

Phytochemical examination and biocidal activity of *Teucrium quadrifarium* Ham.

Sonal Tripathi^{*a}, Om Prakash^b and A. K. Pant^b

^aDepartment of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari-396 450, Gujarat, India

E-mail : sdixit77@gmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, College of Basic Science and Humanities, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar-396 450, Gujarat, India

E-mail : oporgchem@gmail.com, anilk_pant@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : Phytochemical analysis of hexane extract of *Teucrium quadrifarium* resulted in isolation of two steroidal compounds. One compound was identified as (24S)-24-ethylcholesta-5,22(E),25-trien-3 β -ol. This sterol possesses a 24 β -configuration and has previously been reported as constituent of some species belonging to the family Verbenaceae. This compound has also been reported to be present in some other species of *Teucrium*. This could support the view of necessary reclassification of Lamiaceae and Verbenaceae. The second compound could not be identified due to purity reasons and further spectral analysis. HPLC analysis of aerial parts of *T. quadrifarium* revealed the presence of protocathechuic acid, *p*-hydroxy benzoic acid, chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid and syringic acid. The methanolic extract of *T. quadrifarium* revealed no contact toxicity against *Epilachna vigintioctopunctata*. The crude methanolic extract was found ineffective in inhabiting fungus growth and bacteria against the tested organisms. These investigations are of chemotaxonomic significance. Further bioassay investigations are needed to test the potential of *T. quadrifarium* to be used as a botanical pesticide.

Keywords : *Teucrium quadrifarium*, biocidal, phytochemical analysis, phenolics, chemotaxonomic, steroid.

Introduction

Plants are the richest source of renewable organic chemicals. The total number of plant chemicals may exceed 4,00,000. Of these secondary metabolites, 10,000 metabolites play a major role in plant protection and are reportedly defensive against pests¹. Numerous such defensive chemicals belonging to various categories (terpenoids, alkaloids, glycosides, phenols, tannins, etc.), which have behavioral and physiological effects on pests have already been identified². As many as 2,121 plant species have been reported to possess pest control properties, 1,005 species have insecticidal, 384 antifeedant, 297 repellants, 27 attractants and 31 growth inhibiting properties³.

Teucrium species (Lamiaceae) are used worldwide in several systems of indigenous medicine. They have been used in folk medicine in various cultures and several interesting medicinal properties, such as antispasmodic,

antidiabetic, antiulcerogenic, anti-inflammatory and antipyretic have been attributed to them⁴⁻⁸.

Some reports in literature on the diterpenoids of *T. quadrifarium* growing in China have been cited⁹. It has been reported in literature that variation in chemical composition of species can vary under different ecological conditions, places and time of collection and several chemotypes of a single species are present. This evoked us to work on chemistry and biological activity of *T. quadrifarium* found to grow wildy in the Himalayan region of India.

Materials and methods :

Collection of plant material :

The plant collected from Nainital was identified by Dr. Y. P. S. Pangti, Professor (Plant Taxonomist), Department of Botany, Kumaun University, Nainital. The herbarium was deposited and maintained at Department of Chemistry, College of Basic Science and Humanities.

Extraction :

Shade dried and finely powdered aerial parts (≈ 2 kg) were extracted with methanol. The extract was concentrated to dryness in thin film rotatory vacuum evaporator at 30 ± 5 °C. The extract was re-dissolved in 500 mL methanol and diluted with 500 mL of distilled water. The aqua-methanolic extract was then successively extracted using solvent-solvent extraction using separating funnel with hexane, chloroform and ethyl acetate. The hexane, chloroform and ethyl acetate extract were vacuum distilled.

Silica gel column was packed. Hexane and ethyl acetate extract were absorbed in silica gel were loaded on to the column. The column was first eluted in hexane and then mixture of hexane : ethyl acetate (9 : 1) till 100 percent ethyl acetate with increasing concentration of ethyl acetate in hexane.

The hexane extract (23 g) was subjected to column chromatography on silica gel (BDH, 60–120 mesh) deactivated with 15 percent water. Four hundred grams of silica gel was packed in 5 cm \times 60 cm column as slurry in hexane. The dried hexane extract was mixed with 25 g of dried silica and was loaded on to the top of the column. The column was first eluted with hexane and successively with hexane-ethyl acetate mixture. Fractions of 100 mL each were collected and in all 80 fractions were collected. The fractions were monitored by TLC. The plates were developed in hexane : ethyl acetate (9 : 1), benzene : ethyl acetate (9 : 1) and chloroform : acetone (9 : 1). The fractions 7–19 were subjected to TLC using benzene : ethyl acetate in glass chamber and plates were visualized in iodine chamber. The fractions showing single component or similar component or similar compounds were combined for further studies.

Colour test :

Liebermann-Buchard test : One mg of crystalline compound to be tested was dissolved in 0.5 mL chloroform. Three drops of acetic anhydride and two drops of conc. H_2SO_4 were then added to the above solution. A transient purple colour changing to blue and then to green was obtained as a positive reaction of sterol.

Salwoski test : The compound (1 mg) to be tested was dissolved in 0.5 mL chloroform, followed by the addition of two drops of concentrated H_2O_2 . A red tinge was observed in the chloroform layer. This is a characteristic reaction of sterols.

Isolation of phenolic acids :

The samples for quantitative and qualitative determination of phenolic acids present in *T. quadrifarium* were prepared according to the procedure of Charpentioer and Cowlens¹⁰ and analyzed with HPLC¹¹. Phenolics isolated from plant were identified by comparing the retention times with those of authentic compounds.

Insecticidal activity :

Insecticidal activity of methanol extract was tested against three days old grubs of *Epilachna vigintioctopunctata*, contact toxicity method and residue control bioassay method¹² was applied. The concentration of test solution was 10 mg plant extract per mL acetone.

Antifungal activity :

The methanol extract was tested against fungi *Rhizoctoni solani*, *Alternaria brassicae*, *Magnaporthe gresea*, *Fusarium moniliforme*, *Neovosia indica*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Macrophomina phaseoline*. The inhibition zone bioassay¹³ was used for screening of plant extract.

Antibacterial activity :

Inhibition zone bioassay¹³ method was used for screening of plant extract for its antibacterial activity. The methanol extract was tested against *Pseudomonad floescence*, *Bacillus* species, *Escherichia coli*, *Xanthomonas* species and *Sarcinia lutea*.

Results

Phytochemical analysis of hexane extract :

The hexane extract subjected to column chromatography and eluted with hexane and hexane-ethyl acetate mixture. Fraction number 14 showed a single major spot. This fraction was evaporated under vacuum to lead 76 mg of a crystalline solid. This compound showed positive LB test when subjected to TLC and sprayed with LB reagent. The compound was further purified by repetitive crystallizations from methanol : ether (compound A, 32 mg) after five successive crystallizations.

Identification of compound A :

The compound A (m.p. 146–148 °C) specific rotation $[\alpha]_D^{20} -40.6^\circ$ (in chloroform). The IR ν_{max} KBr (cm^{-1}) spectra of compound showed bands at 3440, 3320 (-OH), 3080, 1645, 890 (terminal -CH₂), 3030, 1660, 980, 970, 800 (olefinic double bonds), 2940, 2870, 1460, 1380, 1370, 1060, 1050.

¹H NMR spectra of compound **A** (300 MHz CDCl₃) showed δ 3.52 (1H, septet, $J_{3\alpha 2\beta} = J_{3\alpha 4\beta}$ 9.6 Hz, $J_{3\alpha 4\alpha}$ 5.4 Hz (H-3 α)), 5.35 (1H, brd, J 5.1 Hz (H-6)), 5.24 (1H, dd, J 15.3, 7.9 Hz (H-22)), 5.16 (1H, dd, J 15.3, 16.4 Hz (H-23)), 2.42 (1H, brq, J 6.4 Hz (H-24)), 4.69 (2H, brs, (2H-26)), 0.68 (3H, s, (Me-18)), 1.003 (3H (Me-19)), 1.00 (3H, d, J 6.5 Hz (H-21)), 1.64 (3H, t, J 0.09 Hz (Me-27)), 0.82 (3H, t, J 73 Hz (Me-29)).

EIMS of compound **A** (70 eV, direct inlet) m/z (rel. int.): 410 [M]⁺ (1), 395 (0.5), 392 (0.2), 271 (12), 255 (10), 159 (24), 147 (23), 138 (29), 137 (38), 121 (29), 109 (84), 107 (43), 105 (33), 95 (58), 93 (46), 91 (47), 81 (79), 79 (46), 67 (41), 55 (100), 41 (46).

Ten mg of compound **A** was treated with Ac₂O-pyridine for 24 h. The acetylated mixture was purified with elution with hexane : ethyl acetate (9 : 1) in a small column of silica gel impregnated with AgNO₃. The acetate isolated had melting point 150–153 °C. The above data was in perfect agreement for (24*S*)-24-ethylcholesta-5,22(*E*),25-triene-3 β -ol published in literature¹⁴.

Fraction number 15, 16 and 17 were combined together, to yield 32 mg crystalline solid. This fraction also showed a positive LB test on TLC. The compound was subjected to repetitive crystallization to isolate a relatively pure looking compound (compound **B**).

EIMS of compound **B** showed 412, 381, 363, 327, 314, 300, 271, 255, 213, 199, 159, 137, 119, 159, 137, 119, 109, 95, 81, 67, 55, 42.

¹H NMR spectra of compound **B** (300 MHz, CDCl₃) showed δ 3.52 (1H, septate brd), 5.24 (1H, dd), 5.16 (1H, dd), 2.42 (1H, brq), 4.42 (2H, brs), 1.00 (3H, ds), 1.25 (2H, s), 1.64 (3H, t), 0.82 (3H, t).

The IR spectrum indicates this compound (**B**) to be a sterol. The DEPT and ¹³C NMR spectra of the compound **B** were also recorded. However the compound **B** could not be identified because of purity reasons and further spectral analysis. Further purification of this compound is in progress. The compound **A** isolated was identical in respect to its m.p., $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectrum to (24*S*)-24-ethylcholesta-5,22(*E*),25-trien-3 β -ol, a previously isolated compound from *Clodendrum campbelli* (Verbenaceae) its structure and 24 β -configuration have been elucidated⁵. The presence of this compound in *T. oliverianum*¹⁶, *T. royleanum*¹⁷, *T. abutiloides* and *T. betonicum*¹⁴ have also been reported recently.

β -Sitosterol; 24 α -ethylcholesta-5,25-dien-3 β -ol; 3 β -hydroxy stigmasta-24(24¹), 25-dien-24²-al and 3 β -hydroxy-24 α -ethylcholesta-5,25-dien-7-one have also been isolated from aerial parts of *T. chamaedrys* ssp. *chamaedrys*¹⁸. The data reported for the acetyl derivative of (24*S*)-24-ethylcholesta-5,22(*E*),25-trien-3 β -ol (m.p. 141 °C)¹⁵ did not entirely agree with our results of acetyl derivative of compound **A** (m.p. 150–153 °C), but this may be due to polymorphism or impurities because the ¹H NMR spectra of compound **A** showed the chemical shifts and coupling values of the H-22 and H-23 olefinic protons identical with those reported for (24*S*)-3 β -acetoxy-24-ethyl-5 α -cholesta-7,22(*E*),25-trienes. The difference between the chemical shifts of the H-22 and H-23, protons in compound **A** (0.08 and 0.06 ppm, respectively) was identical to that observed in (24*S*)-24 β derivatives (0.08 ppm)¹⁹. From a chemotaxonomic point of view²⁰ it is important to indicate that the sterol (compound **A**) isolated from *T. quadrifarium* possesses a 24 β -configuration and has previously been reported as constituent of some species belonging to the family Verbenaceae^{21,14}. Although, apparently, development and plant anatomy may influence the sterol composition²².

Phenolic acids from Teucrium quadrifarium :

The quantitative estimation revealed that the amount of phenolic acid, *p*-hydroxy benzoic acid, chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid and syringic acid in leaves of *T. quadrifarium* were 0.11, 0.36, 0.08, 0.12 and 0.85 μ g/10 g respectively. The phenolics are well known for disease resistance in plants. It would therefore, not be surprising that these may provide chemical defense to the plant against pest, but further confirmation to the view requires extensive bioassay tests with individual phenolics in order to ascertain their potentiality.

Insecticidal activity :

Insecticidal activity of methanolic extract was tested against *Epilachna vigintioctopunctata* three days old grubs at a concentration of 10 mg per mL acetone. At this concentration it did not lead to mortality of insect. Thus indicating that, plant extract does not have insecticidal property at this concentration. Higher concentrations were not tested because of unpractical and uneconomical reasons.

Antifungal activity :

The methanolic extract of *T. quadrifarium* did not

show antifungal activity at a concentration of 8 mg extract per ml of acetone against tested organisms.

Antibacterial activity :

The preliminary antibacterial assay showed that the methanolic extract of *T. quadrifarium* gave no inhibition zone at concentration of 8 mg extract per mL of acetone against tested bacteria. So extract cannot be considered as having antibacterial activity.

Conclusion

Phytochemical analysis of hexane extract of *T. quadrifarium* by chromatographic method resulted in isolation of two steroidal compounds. One was identified as (24S)-24-ethylcholesta-5,22(E),25-trien-3 β -ol by its IR, ¹H NMR and Mass spectral data and comparison with published data in the literature. This sterol isolated from *T. quadrifarium* possess a 24 β configuration and has previously been reported as the constituent of some species belonging to the family Verbenaceae. This compound has also been reported to be present in some other species of *Teucrium* viz. *T. oliverianum*¹⁶, *T. royleanum*¹⁷, *T. abutiloides* and *T. betonicum*¹⁴. This could support the view of necessary reclassification of Lamiaceae and Verbenaceae. The IR spectrum of second compound indicates it to be a sterol with molecular weight 412. The recorded ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR data indicates that, this is not a pure compound. However, the compound could not be identified due to purity reasons and further spectral analysis. The aerial parts of *T. quadrifarium* were found to be rich in protocatechuic acid, *p*-hydroxy benzoic acid, chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid and syringic acid. The methanolic extract did not show insecticidal, antifungal and antibacterial activity against tested organisms at 10 mg and 8 mg of crude methanolic extract per mL of acetone respectively. The investigations are of chemotaxonomic significance. Further bioassay investigations are needed to test the potential of *T. quadrifarium* to be used as a botanical pesticide.

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